

LINGUISTIC INTERFERENCE IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION: THE INFLUENCE OF KARAKALPAK ON ENGLISH LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This article explores linguistic interference in second language acquisition, with a particular focus on the influence of the Karakalpak language on the English learning process. Linguistic interference refers to the impact of one's mother tongue on learning or using a second language, often resulting in errors in grammar, word choice, pronunciation, and comprehension. This study identifies and analyzes the most common types of mistakes made by Karakalpak speakers during their English language acquisition.

Introduction

Linguistic interference, also known as language interference or cross-linguistic influence, is a phenomenon in language learning where the knowledge of a speaker's first language (L1) affects the acquisition and use of a second language (L2). This concept is part of a broader process called transfer, which refers to the application of previously learned knowledge to new situations. In language learning, transfer becomes particularly noticeable when learners apply rules or sounds from their first language to the second language, sometimes leading to errors. When speakers of Karakalpak, for example, learn English, they often experience negative transfer due to differences in the phonetic and grammatical systems of the two languages.

Negative Transfer Examples

A common example is that speakers of Karakalpak often face challenges with certain English sounds that do not exist in their native language. A notable issue is the difficulty in pronouncing the English "th" sound. Since Karakalpak does not have this sound, learners might substitute it with "t" or "d," resulting in pronunciation errors like saying "tink" instead of "think" or "dis" instead of "this." According to Selinker (1992), such phonetic interference is common when the learner's first language lacks certain sounds present in the target language, often leading to predictable substitution patterns.

Negative interference is typically divided into two categories: overgeneralization and interference. Overgeneralization occurs when a learner applies a rule too broadly within the L2. An example might be an English learner adding "-ed" to all verbs to form the past tense, regardless of irregular forms. Interference, on the other hand, refers specifically to the direct influence of L1 on L2, which can result in incorrect grammar, pronunciation, or usage patterns.

Error Analysis

The analysis of errors revealed recurring patterns across various linguistic elements, notably in areas such as word order, article usage, plural forms, double negatives, gender pronouns and pronunciation.

1. Word Order Interference:

Karakalpak: "Meniń úyim bar" – literally "My house is."

English Mistake: "My house is" instead of "I have a house."

In Karakalpak, the verb often comes at the end of the sentence, whereas in English, the structure is subject-verb-object. Odlin (1989) highlights that syntactic interference is frequent when the L1 and L2 have fundamentally different sentence structures, which often causes difficulty in producing fluent, grammatically correct sentences in the L2.

2. Article Usage:

Karakalpak: Karakalpak does not have articles like "a" or "the."

English Mistake: Omitting articles: "I bought book" instead of "I bought a book."

Explanation: Since Karakalpak does not use articles, learners might forget to include them in English sentences.

3.1 Pluralization:

Karakalpak: Plural is often indicated by the suffix "-lar" or "-ler" (e.g., "kitaplar" for "books").

English Mistake: Adding "-s" to all nouns, regardless of whether they are irregular (e.g., "tooths" for "teeth" or "sheeps" for "sheep"). Additionally, Karakalpak speakers might omit the plural suffix when specifying a number, such as saying "stoldiń ústinde 3 kitap bar" instead of "there are 3 books on the table."

Explanation: The way plurals are formed in Karakalpak and the absence of plural suffixes with numbers might lead learners to apply English plural rules inconsistently, either by overgeneralizing or omitting necessary plural forms.

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4. Double Negatives:

Karakalpak: Meniń hesh nárssem joq. – literally meaning "I have no nothing" (instead of "I have nothing")

English Mistake: "I don't have nothing" instead of "I don't have anything."

Explanation: In Karakalpak, double negatives are used for emphasis, but in English, they create a positive statement instead of a negative one.

5. Gender Pronouns:

Karakalpak: Karakalpak does not distinguish between male and female pronouns; "ol" can mean "he," "she," or "it."

English Mistake: Confusing "he" and "she": "She is my brother" instead of "He is my brother."

Explanation: The absence of gender-specific pronouns in Karakalpak can lead to confusion when using them in English.

6. Pronunciation:

Karakalpak is a phonetic language, meaning words are pronounced as they are written. In contrast, English is a non-phonetic language, where many words are not spelled as they sound.

This can create challenges for Karakalpak speakers when learning English, as they may expect the pronunciation to match the written form. For instance, they might struggle with words like "enough," which is written differently than how it is pronounced, causing confusion and mispronunciations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, linguistic interference plays a significant role in second language acquisition, particularly when learners' first and second languages differ in their phonetic and grammatical systems. The influence of the Karakalpak language on English learning showcases how negative transfer can manifest in specific pronunciation and grammatical errors and overgeneralization of grammatical rules. Understanding these interference patterns is crucial for educators in designing targeted teaching strategies that address the unique challenges faced by Karakalpak speakers. By recognizing the specific sources of interference, language instructors can better support learners in overcoming these obstacles, leading to more effective language acquisition and reduced error rates in English proficiency.

References:

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